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Defining the Purpose of Pastoral Education in the Artificial Intelligence Era: A Study of a Pastoral Education Department of a Christian School in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Pastoral education is a determinant of pastoral duties and practices which include teaching, mentoring, counselling, witnessing, and preaching. There are many challenges that pastors face in carrying out their duties. Apart from personal challenges, the pastors are also faced with societal, economic, political, and technological challenges. The purpose of pastoral education is to equip pastors to effectively carry out their roles. The technological advancement has gone beyond the imagination of many people, particularly the evolution of Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI has made machines that execute duties of humans intelligently. Machines perform surgical operation, write papers, buy things, drive vehicles, interact with humans, but more than this, they have started being used to carry out pastoral roles like preaching and teaching. If machine can execute pastor's duties what then is the purpose of pastoral education? Different studies have been done on how AI affects Christianity generally, but not much has been done in regards to defining purpose of pastoral education in the era of AI. Using discipling theory, this paper adopted phenomenology design of qualitative research, to examine the need to clearly define the purpose of pastoral education that will be relevant in the age of AI. It was found that AI and its usage should be appropriately integrated into pastoral education but should not replace the roles of human. The purpose of pastoral education is to prepare people who have passion for Christ to go and make disciples. Teachers in the seminaries need to update themselves and be current. It was concluded that since the purpose of pastoral education remains equipping people to make disciples, AI should be used when necessary but should not replace humans where needed especially in instilling practical approach of discipling to students.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Christ Representative, Pastoral Education, Surgical Operation, Technological Development

Introduction

Many duties that human beings carry out intelligently for centuries — teaching, counselling, manufacturing, marketing, relationships— are going through redefinition and restructuring as a result of the emergence and evolution of technological advancement especially the Artificial Intelligence (AI) which is replacing machines for humans in carrying out these duties. Artificial Intelligence according to Robin (2018) is the ability of a digital computer, computer-controlled machine or robot to perform roles and activities that are commonly associated with intelligent humans. He added that AI even performs many smarter activities than humans. Scholars have argued that AI has become increasingly prominent in education with enormous potential to improve teaching and learning experiences (Nurjanah, Salsabia, Azzahra, Rahayu, & Marlina, 2024). Pastoral education is an essential part of pastoral ministry as it is the avenue through which pastors are prepared and equipped to carry their duties effectively in church and in the society. Pastors serve as teachers, counselors, preachers, mentors, peacemakers, even caregiver in many communities where they find themselves. The ability to perform these roles many times depends on the type of pastoral education received by the pastors. Therefore, the purpose of pastoral education is to effectively prepare and equip pastors to carry out their pastoral duties. The preparing and equipping are done by qualified and experienced individuals who by themselves who have been prepared and equipped, and also are experienced in pastoral responsibilities.

With the evolution of AI and its taking over every duty performed by humans, including teaching and preaching, there is a need to define the purpose of pastoral education in the AI era.

Literature Review

Pastoral education which is also known as Christian religious education, theological education, and Christian education (Marbaniang, 2018) is a system of education in which pastors are prepared and equipped to serve in different capacities in the Christian church and in the society where they find themselves as pastors. Marbaniang (2018) differentiated between this type of education and religious education. Religious education according to him can be a study in any type of religion that may not necessarily be Christian; but pastoral education deals specifically on preparing pastors for discharging Christian duties in Christian church and beyond. Pastoral education also deals with exegesis and hermeneutic which is the equipping of pastors in interpretation of biblical passages from original languages (Hebrew and Greek) and making biblical passages relevant to everyday life of people. This understanding of the pastoral education indicates its theological aspect. An important thing is that pastoral education with all the exegesis and hermeneutic expertise do not make a pastor without the influence of the Holy Spirit.

Sometimes pastoral education may not necessarily be formal; it can be formal, non-formal, and informal (Marbaniang, 2018). Pastoral education is more than just its content but equipping pastors in educational system that is distinctively Christian, reflecting biblical truth as found in Christ Jesus (Estep Jr., 2008). It is taking someone through the process of transformation in which the whole individual is changes into the likeness of Christ. It is the process that establishes pastors in the position of pastoring. Otokola (2017) presented it as the training of men and women to know and serve God. Therefore, pastoral education is not only acquiring theoretical knowledge of biblical interpretation and skill of preaching, but it is going through heart transformation and becoming like Christ (Anthony, 2008). Education originated from God and it is about God and it is to lead back to God (Abolarin, 2015; Otokola, 2017). Since creation, God has always established systems of education to have people know him. In the Old Testament, God used the sanctuary/sacrificial system and prophetic system; in the New Testament, he came to human society as the “good teacher” in the person of Jesus Christ who demonstrated and gave the perfect teaching method that the apostles followed (Reed & Prevost, 1993).

A pastor that has gone through the pastoral education is considered to have received requisite level of academic understanding and practical ministerial training to function spiritual caregiver to people (Marbaniang, 2020). Byaruhanga (2013) and Morris (2018) identified the benefits of pastoral education to include

1. In-person instruction: pastoral education gives opportunity for face-to-face instruction from teacher to students which allows for growth both in the students and in the teacher.
2. Equipping for mentoring: the physical teaching through pastoral education allows for mentoring process to naturally occur between teacher and students. Mentoring is many times, imitating the mentor by the mentee which takes place person-to-person.
3. Discipleship: this is almost like mentoring but it has to do with motivating and equipping someone to know and follow Jesus Christ and becoming like him. Pastoral education furnishes this opportunity.
4. Growth through deeper study: pastoral education has ability to make students experience deep study of both the Bible and other Christian religious literature which leads to personal growth in the students and prepares them to transmit such to those they come in contact with.
5. Developing teaching skill: through pastoral education, students can develop skills in teaching which can be profitable in carrying out their duties.

6. Building of healthy church: pastoral education is an avenue through which pastors are trained to go and build healthy church after the educational process.
7. Contextual ministry: pastoral education is a process through which pastors are trained to be sensitive to the needs of the people and minister to the people in the context of their needs, making ministering relevant and meaningful.

Speaking on the pastoral education in West Africa, Gyadu (2013) argued that many institutions have been established for the training of pastors and this has positively helped the growth of the Christianity. Despite this growth, Oluwashola and Paul (2020) indicated that pastoral ministry which ought to be the output of the pastoral education, has not fulfilled its goal of presenting the full gospel truth. According to them, the pastoral ministry in Nigeria is filled with preaching the popular gospel of health and wealth; and many pastors preach half-backed Christians. Apart from this challenge, AI is another possible threat to achieving the purpose of pastoral education.

AI era is the period of human history when machines and robots are used to discharge the duties that are commonly known to be carried out by human. Such duties include farming, medical care, business transaction, educational practices, and preaching. In addition to these, transportation services are being handled by AI. Although AI is not new to human existence (Lim, 2023), its evolution to the level of taking over and executing what human would intelligently execute, thereby directly or indirectly replacing human beings in almost every dimension of life—teaching, preaching, buying, diagnosis and medication administration, surgery—has given an ease or a discomfort to people. Lim (2023) indicated that dealing with an inanimate object (software application) that acts like human being and looking at the synthetic faces generated by AI the negative response known as “uncanny valley” comes in and the sense of what is real becomes confused.

AI is a system’s ability to behave intelligently as human, interpreting external data correctly, learning from such data and using the learning to achieve specific goals and tasks through flexible adaptation (Haenlein & Kaplan, 2019). AI is the ability of a digital computer, computer-controlled machine or robot to perform roles and activities that are meant for human. Different individuals have written about the benefits of AI (Chakraborty, 2024; Lakhani, 2023; Vargas, 2023) however, there are concerns as well concerning its impact on human endeavor.

Education is one of the aspects of human life that AI has influenced. According to Slimi (2023), AI impacts school accuracy in enrollment, curriculum and is replacing lecturer in many ways. AI is considered to be an appropriate methodology to train teachers because of its effectiveness (Porayska-Pomsta, 2016). There are classes that hold virtually and assessments are done using computer system, and students interact with virtual classroom. Although AI plays a significant role in revolutionizing education, Milberg (2024) warned that only through responsible and informed adoption can it truly fulfil its potential and ensure equitable access to quality education. In essence, AI has the tendency to negatively influence acquisition of knowledge. There is a concern on the impossibility of AI replacing human in every aspect. Based on this concern, there is a need to determine which skills to prioritize, which one to phase out and where to place greater emphasis. In addition to this, consideration should be on how the goal of education will not be compromised. Education is not just about intellectual but also social, physical and spiritual (Abolarin, 2019). Clugston (2024) argued that with all the benefits (innovative teaching, interactive learning environment, accessibility, efficiency, and personalized learning) of AI in education, teachers (humans) are to focus on instruction and student engagement. This indicates that machine/robot is not to be entrusted with everything in educational practices. Some of the disadvantages of AI in education according to Clugston (2024) include data privacy compromise, dependence on technology, lack of human touch which leads to dehumanized learning experience, risk of cheating, and teacher job displacement.

When it comes to AI and pastoral education, Olaore, Nwosu, Oladipo, and Oyenuga (2014) argued that natural intelligence is divine with origin that is unlimited but AI is from limited origin (human). AI therefore, according to them should be seen as human creature and subordinate to human and not their replacement. Considering whether AI could deliver pastoral care, Proudfoot (2023) considering Noreen Herzfeld work that utilized Karl Barth's framework of I-Thou encounters as a heuristic for measuring the relational capacity of AI, rejected the idea of I-Thou encounter between human and machine because, according to her, machine lacks a relationship with God. It is possible for machine to be an autonomous agent but machine cannot develop the awareness of God and therefore cannot have relationship with God. In essence, there is a question on the possibility of machine to assist in spiritual dimension of pastoral care. Pastoral education is not just about intellectual development but more of connection with God and to be equipped by him to become agent of connecting others to the same God. The three things that must be part of anyone who engage in such education are self-awareness, a rational governing soul, and the equipping by the Spirit for a covenantal relationship with God. To be engaged in pastoral education, there must be ability to identify a specific person, to provide interaction with the rest of creation, and to take initiative in promoting certain actions; without these there cannot be inter-human relationship. In pastoral education there must be a kind of feeling of "one like me" between teacher and students. There must also be mutual speaking and hearing with another communicating who each one is and the goal of the communication. There should be ability of each one to render help to the other, willing to respond to the request of one another.

Therefore, considering all the characteristics required in getting engaged in pastoral education, a non-human artificial conscious being would not be a replacement for human. Proudfoot (2023) concluded in his study that if conscious computer is engaged in pastoral care, which by extension includes pastoral education, the care will be shallow than human can provide. Whatever be the educational approach adopted in pastoral education, the purpose of the education must always be defined, established and guarded. It is the purpose that determines the approach and the methodology to be adopted in the educational practices.

The discipling theory as established by Hull (2004) indicated that the process of making disciples which is a major goal of pastoral education should be engaged by human to human. The theory is divided into four parts. The first part is calling people to "come and see" (p. 32). This is an invitation to behold Jesus which is done by someone who has beheld Jesus already. After beholding Jesus, the second part of the theory which calls for the commitment to Jesus. This is the call to follow Jesus. It is an indication of commitment to him. The third part of the theory is to become a member of the community of Jesus, "come and abide with me" (p. 147). The fourth part of the theory calls individual to remain in Jesus. This is becoming competent in him making other disciples. Hull (2006) stated that this process which is the focus of the training in pastoral education requires persons who are passionate for Christ. In essence non-human may be able to perform certain areas of teaching and equipping in pastoral education process, but only humans who are passionate for Christ can make another passionate individual who will "sustain any effort to reach others around them?" (p. 37). If the preparation of the people (pastors) who are to make disciples are not done by those who are passionate for Jesus, which anything other than human may not, Christian truth and behavior may gradually disappear (Wilson, 1976). Humans who are passionate and radical for Jesus are to be engaged (Augsburger, 2006) in preparing those who are to lead his church and equip people to live for Jesus.

Objective

The objective of this paper is to investigate how pastoral education purpose could be defined in this era of AI.

Methodology

Phenomenology design of qualitative research was used for this paper. This allowed for interaction with students and teachers in pastoral education in a Christian institution of learning. Fulfilling the purpose of pastoral education was considered to be a phenomenon that needs to be defined adequately in the era of AI. Purposive sampling technique was used to select teachers and students in pastoral education department specifically in a Christian institution in Ogun State. The total number of the participants was 25 comprising four teachers and 21 students. The paper utilized interview as an approach for data collection and interview guide was used as the instrument. The teachers were interviewed on individual basis while the students formed a focus group. The interview was conducted on face-to-face basis. The major questions posted to the participants include, what is pastoral education? What is the purpose of pastoral education? What is AI and how has it influenced education? How should the purpose of pastoral education be properly defined in this era of AI? Content analysis based on the questions was adopted for the analysis of the data collected.

Findings

Question 1: What is pastoral education?

Responses: Pastoral education was presented by the respondents as a kind of process which people who believe they are called by God to serve as pastor, go through for them to be knowledgeable and be equipped with necessary skills to serve as Pastors. The skills include Bible interpretation, communication, personal and public ministry, counselling, public speaking, teaching, and writing. If God calls someone to serve as pastor, it is still necessary for the person to experience educational process to affirm the calling. Sometime, someone who is called may not be opportune to acquire formal education; this is why both informal and non-formal aspect of pastoral education is important. Those who cannot attend a degree awarding institution can attend local training organized for pastors. There are different workshops and conferences where individuals can attend to acquire knowledge. Any form of enlightening program for pastors can serve as pastoral education. Pastoral education is an avenue of preparing pastors as spiritual leaders trained to work for God by connecting people to him for them to be saved. It is a special grooming of people who perceived to have been called to meet spiritual and holistic needs of people by nurturing them to grow in God's way. It is to prepare the "called" to transmit God's message of love for the salvation of people. As spiritual leaders, pastors go through pastoral educational system to ensure their own connection with Jesus through which they can connect people to him without leading them astray this is by continuous acquirement of knowledge from God.

Pastoral education also helps pastors to understand and know God and his creation. Pastoral education connects people to God and assist in developing lasting relationship with God. This relationship is demonstrated in the daily life and interactions of pastors with people around him/her.

Question 2: What is the purpose of pastoral education?

Like any other discipline, pastors need to be trained in the knowhow of pastoral ministry; and that is what pastoral education does. Just as other aspects, especially the professional aspects of human life, cannot be handled by those who have no knowledge in the profession, so also the pastoral discipline/profession cannot be committed to people without adequate knowledge and skills to discharge pastoral duties. Pastoral education is a specialized system for acquiring necessary knowledge and skills to carry out pastoral duties. It enlightens pastors in different aspect of spirituality. There are different spirituality practices being executed by people of different religions. Pastoral education is particular about exposing pastors to the different practices and focus pastors mind on the Christian spiritual practices which acknowledge God as the Creator and sustainer of lives. It is to him all humans are accountable and will give account. Humans are to live their

lives in fulfilling his purpose for them while here on earth. This understanding is crucial to every other aspect of life. This makes pastoral education a critical experience for pastors.

Pastoral education as an experience is for connecting pastors to God and prepares them to be representatives of the kingdom of God here on earth. This is essential because if pastors are not connected to God, it will be challenging if not impossible for them to connect other people. So, pastoral education helps pastors connect for them to be able to connect others to God.

It trains pastors in counselling procedure. Since pastors work for God by working with humans, it is important for pastors to understand different aspects of human life which include emotion, psychology, habit, appearance, problems, joy, and interrelationship. Adequate understanding of these aspects of human living helps pastors to minister to people in all the aspects; this makes pastoral ministry a holistic one. Pastors engage in this holistic ministry through, teaching, preaching, and counseling. Pastoral education is an important system for preparing pastors for the holistic ministry, getting them ready to engage in counseling program.

It equips pastors with tools to interpret Bible passages and present it to people. Pastoral ministry is beyond only reading Bible passages and telling it to people; but rather, it involves proper interpretation of each Bible passage to understand the meaning and application to the needs of people. In doing this pastoral education exposes pastors to biblical passages interpretation through the use of original languages in which the Bible was written. The languages include Hebrew, Greek, and Latin. Pastor study and learn how to interpret these languages thereby equipping them to have the original understanding of Bible passages.

Question 3: What is AI and how has it influenced education?

The respondents presented AI in different ways such as a tool made to perform the roles of human beings, a technological advancement that has come to stay and influencing many ways people do things, and computerized robots that are revolutionizing human capacities and relationships. According to some of the respondents, "AI has been in existence for many years and it is been utilized by many people. Examples of AI include, telephone and computer with different applications that help human to achieve what ordinarily would not have been easily achievable by humans."

Education, according to the respondents, has been influenced in many ways from teaching to learning and assessment of students. Teachers have access to resources and information in an easy way than before the arrival of AI; they also deliver lectures easily using different computerized equipment such as smartboard, computerized screen, and projector. Students also have access to lectures, even video recording of lectures and practical application on different subjects. People can attend class from the comfort of their homes or at distance virtually.

The respondents clarified that despite the positive influence AI has on education, it is not without some negative effects. According to the respondents, AI has made some individuals to not desire physical attendance in church during worship, they prefer virtual worship. This has reduced the potency of Christianity and Christian gathering on people's lives. The aspect of *koinonia* (community, togetherness) is not important to many. People go into depression because they live individualistic life, not relating to others nor share their burdens again. In some cases, AI has been a distraction from spiritual growth and connection with God for people. Pastors use AI to prepare sermon without any consultation with the Holy Spirit nor the Bible. People listen to such sermon but they are not positively impacted. Considering the negative effect of AI, one of the respondents exclaimed, "the world needs prayer." Many of the respondents made reference to Daniel 12:4 "Many shall run to and from, and knowledge shall increase" as being fulfilled with the evolution of AI; but they connected the passage with Matthew 24:12 that read, "because iniquity shall abound, the love of many shall wax cold."

The respondents emphasized that AI can make pastors become lazy by not spending quality time in prayer and study of the Bible to come up with messages for their members. When such happens, irrelevant messages may be presented to congregation.

Question 4: How should the purpose of pastoral education be properly defined in this era of AI?

The respondents declared that AI can also have negative impact on pastoral education. They clarify this idea by stating that just as AI is making information available to people without attending school/class, it can also make pastors to secure any information needed—biblical interpretation, exegetical study, hermeneutics, homiletics—without necessarily going through pastoral education. Therefore, pastoral education, according to them should be re-defined by utilization of AI tools. There should be no pretense in pastoral education practices that AI does not exist but rather, it should be acknowledged and used as much as possible to expose the pastoral students to the usage, the negative effect and how to avoid it. Pastoral education should equip students with the technological know-how for them to be aware of their environment and learn the positive usage of the technology. Pastoral education has to balance the use of AI and doing what humans are to do by themselves, like praying, studying the Bible, having compassion for people, and visiting people. In essence, there should not be over-reliance on AI by pastors.

AI has come to stay and cannot be done away with; pastoral education should embrace and utilize it positively to equip pastoral education students who will eventually be pastors. Pastoral education should watch out for intellectual cloning and colonization where individuals cannot develop their God given potential because of dependence on AI. The influence of the Holy Spirit should not be replaced with suggestion of AI; pastoral education should emphasize the place and role of the Holy Spirit in the era of AI and teach how the Holy Spirit can use AI to achieve God's purpose. AI should be made a subset of pastoral education and people should be encouraged to go back to church since the Bible itself says "And let us not neglect our meeting together" (Hebrews 10:25). Pastoral education should make people masters of the Bible and not solely depend on AI. Pastoral educators should update themselves in technological field, especially AI and use it to teach coupled with their personal experience which AI cannot offer. Jesus Christ example of compassion and empathy which AI cannot provide should be part of pastoral education.

Discussion of Findings

The findings indicate that both teachers and students of pastoral education acknowledge pastoral education as an important means through which pastors are trained and equipped for pastoral ministry. Irrespective of skills in ministering, attending and experiencing pastoral education is a need factor to function as pastor. This perspective is according to the argument of Pliska (2023) who stated that any man aspiring to ministry should be trained. Although, formal pastoral education is important, there is a room for informal training for those who may not be opportune to attend formal education. The important thing is that it is not an ideal for anyone to declare being a pastor without acquiring pastoral training.

AI is well-known with the reality that it has come to stay. It is not new but has been in use by people for some decades. Though, AI may have negative impact, there are many areas it is beneficial to education generally and pastoral education specifically. It should be incorporated into pastoral education in every aspect it could enhance teaching and learning; but there should be not over-dependence on it. Education in the current era cannot only be analogue based as it was centuries ago. The goal of pastoral education is to prepare people who are to make disciples of all nations, tongues and people. Where it these individuals cannot be, AI can be used to take the message of the everlasting gospel there without time, location or any hindrance. Therefore, pastoral education should purposively engage pastoral education students in the understanding and usage of AI while the purpose is still well defined without compromise. AI could be seen as an essential tool to enhance learning, equipping, and skill acquisition. Pastoral education should still emphasize the

establishment of God as the Creator, the Bible as the holy manual for living, and the Holy Spirit as the agent of God for information, leaning, and direction. Jesus model of ministry is to be the focus of pastoral education in the era of AI. As AI is to be utilized in pastoral education, pastoral and biblical messages should also be uploaded for people to access through AI tools.

Conclusion

Pastoral education is a necessity in any age as long as the world exists. Its benefits—equipping for ministry, inculcating ministry of compassion, biblical interpretation, preparation of messages that meet the needs of people, training to be like Jesus—cannot be substituted by any other means. In the era of AI, pastoral education can be more effective and easier by utilizing AI tool positively. AI can also be a medium of proclamation of the gospel in an easier and faster way. Therefore, pastoral educators should not be ignorant of the different AI tools and should be inculcated into pastoral education practices, being used by teachers and training students to use them for the ministry. The position of God, the Bible, and the Holy Spirit should not be given up AI. God created all things including humans and humans made AI. AI is to be tools and not ministers. Ministry of compassion, human touch, connecting with one another, following Jesus' model should be the focus of pastoral education.

Recommendations

1. Pastoral education should be acknowledged as a necessity in the era of AI as it was in the Bible time. Christian leaders should not trade pastoral education for any other form of education that will not fulfill the purpose of pastoral ministry.
2. Pastoral education should be equipped by the school administrators with every facility, including AI tools that will make teaching and learning easy and exciting. Pastoral educators should always update themselves in every technological knowhow. There is no need to be afraid of AI but rather pastoral educators should be knowledgeable and teach students how to use it.
3. The roles of God, the Bible and study of the Bible, the Holy Spirit should not be substituted with AI.
4. Jesus' model of ministry should be emphasized in pastoral education and be inculcated to students.

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